

PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS OF LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article is about the paremiological units of the language, namely, the issues of paremiological units' similarities, and distinctions, including proverbs, sayings, phrasaligical units, aphorisms, parables, fables and other paremiological units. This article summarizes and analyzes linguistic material on the Uzbek language.

Keywords: paremiological units, proverb, sayings, rhyme, idioms, linguists.

Introduction. In particular when we think about the paremiology of Uzbek language, first of all "what is paremia" we need to find an answer to the question. Paremiology is a Greek word meaning, a deep meaning, a wise word, a phrase, a proverb, and fable. The paremiological fund of the language represents the valuable linguistic heritage of the people, reflect their culture, traditions, and history. Paremiology reflects people's attitude to various spheres of life and events, such as family, work society. Paremiology (Greek: *paromia* is a wise word) in a certain language transmitted from generation to generation in oral form, concise and simple, short and meaningful, appearing as a logical generalization, a branch of science that studies wise expressions such as proverbs, sayings, aphorisms. The representatives of folklore call the field that studies proverbs and sayings paremiology. Because paremiology is passed down from generation to generation only orally, they are a product of folk and creativity.

Proverbs and sayings are a particularly important element of spiritual culture. Proverbs have the characteristics of "stability, readiness, possessing figurative meaning and not having author. The purpose of proverbs is to serve as an assessment of anything or some phenomenon. Aphorisms are characterized by stability, readiness, ownership of the author while riddles are characterized by stability, readiness of the author. Paremiology has long been of interest to scientists. Aristotle was the first to classify and systematize proverbs and sayings. In every speech people usually use several proverbs, this process gives a lively and powerful meaning to

the conversation between the speaker and the listener. Folk proverbs not only instruct people, but also warn of future joys and sorrows. There is no person who would not use proverbs in his speech. Examples of proverbs in different languages.

In English: better late than never.

A stitch in time saves nine.

Lives without figs.

The best fish smell when they are three days old.

There is no fire without fuel.

There is no rose without a thorn.

IN UZBEK: barakat mag'zida - hunarli qo'l og'zida.

Avval bil, keyin qil.

Soyda yotma sel olar- qirda yotma yel olar.

Idioms: idioms are also colloquial because they consist of several words that are usually used together, but the difference is that we can not guess the meaning of the entire phrase from the meaning of its parts. This criterion is called the level of semantic isolation. It is used in different ways in different expressions. For example: cat got your tongue mean can't you speak?

Snug as a bug in a rug = warm and cozy.

Go the extra mile = make an extra effort.

Butterflies in my stomach = feeling nervous.

To go down in flames = to fail spectacularly.

Cheapskate- mean a person who does not like spending money.

Tongue twisters. Tongue twisters are a kind of Uzbek folklore. Sentences are made up of rhyming words that can be mispronounced. Tongue twisters are a great way to practice and improve pronunciation and fluency. They can also help to improve accents by using alliteration which is repetition of one sound. For instance:

In English: Tom threw three free throws.

I wish to wash my Irish wristwatch.

I scream, you scream , we all scream for ice cream.

We surely shall see the sun shine soon.

In Uzbek: bosh qotirma boltavoyning boshini qotirdi.

Soqi toqqa bordi, boqi boqqa bordi.

Asad asil asal saqladi.

Boqi botir buzoq boqar.

Rhyme. A rhyme is the repetitions so sounds between two words, usually the sounds after the final stressed syllable of each word.

Cat- hat, rotten- forgotten, heard- beard are examples of rhyming pairs of words. Their sounds match after the last stressed syllable.

The collection and study of paremiology continues from the times of Uzbek linguist Mahmud Koshgari (Devoni lug'otit turk) and Gulxaniy (Zarbulmasal) to the present day. Foreign linguists A. Taylor , V Meader dealt with paremiological units. Under the term Paremia researchers understand, first of all proverbs and word units in the context of the origin of the people. But there is also a broader definition of the term. For example: G.S Vorkachue includes not only proverbs and fixed word combinations. But also riddles, proverbs and aphorisms. The formation of paremiology as A science dates back to the beginning of the last century and primarily associated with the name A. Taylor, it provides a wealth of theoretical resources of proverb, sayings and similes. The study of paremiology is the task of such disciplines as psychology , literary studies, history folklore studies.

Conclusion: in short, every country has its own language culture , words, that enrich it . And the idioms, proverbs, phrase, riddles used here are analyzed in the category of paremiology because their creation is associated with the oral art of people in different languages, lifestyle, culture. Above, we examined idioms, proverbs and rhymes which created Uzbek and English.

References

1. Sapir, E. (1929). A study in phonetic symbolism. Journal of Experimental Psychology, 12(3), 225–239.
2. Geeraerts, D. (2010). Theories of lexical semantics. Oxford University Press.

3. Wierzbicka, A. (1992). *Semantics, culture, and cognition: Universal human concepts in culture-specific configurations*. Oxford University Press.
4. QulmamatovaMuattar Otabek qizi. (2023). The Role of Concept in Linguistics. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies* (2993-2599), 1(10), 50–53. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJRCS/article/view/1861>
5. Ibragimova HilolaBahodirjon Qizi, &To'liqinova Maftuna Hasan qizi. (2023). DEBATE TECHNOLOGY AS AN INTERACTIVE FORM OF TEARNING IN ENGLISH CLASSES. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 2(4), 56–59. Retrieved from <https://ojs.rmasav.com/index.php/ojs/article/view/966>
6. QulmamatovaMuattar Otabek qizi. (2023). TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF MEDICAL TERMS. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education, Technology and Management*, 2(4), 39–46. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7796602>
7. QulmamatovaMuattar Otabek qizi, Safarova Farida Normurotovna (2021). The Features of a Good Translator in Translating Medical Terms. *Analytical journal of education and development*, (2181-2624) <https://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/ajed/article/view/526/505>
8. Сафарова, Д. А. (2018). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТОПОНИМОВ В РУССКОМ И УЗБЕКСКИХ ЯЗЫКАХ. *Гуманитарный трактат*, (37), 26-27.
9. Akhmedova Adolat Ravshan kizi. (2022). Problems of Formation of Phonetic Competence of Students (A Level 1). *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 6, 160–162. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/esh/article/view/919>
10. SoatmurodovaShoxista Zafar qizi. (2023). ANALYSIS OF THE BORROWINGS RELATED TO THE FIELD OF “ATTAR” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 95–97. Retrieved from <https://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/966>
11. Ibragimova, H. B. qizi.(2022). INGLIZ TILINI O'QITISHDA PODKASTLAR VA ULARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AMALIY JIHATLARI. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 1(8), 212–219. Retrieved from <http://academics.uz/index.php/rnsr/article/view/1118>